

The Phenomenon of 'Value Extraction' in Open Access

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Abstract

Open Access (OA) agreements were introduced to remove financial barriers to scientific dissemination and to promote equity in access to knowledge. However, as OA publishing costs have shifted from individual authors to institutions, we argue that institutional OA agreements can be used as leverage to obtain authorship or corresponding authorship without proportional intellectual contribution, a phenomenon that we describe as 'value extraction' in OA. We argue that such practices constitute a distinct class of integrity risk in scientific publishing, in which access to publishing infrastructure is converted into academic credit through metric-driven evaluation systems. Here we discuss how OA agreements, when coupled with traditional performance metrics such as publication counts, journal prestige, and corresponding authorship, can exacerbate global and institutional asymmetries, while remaining insufficiently addressed by existing research integrity frameworks. We propose concrete institutional-, publisher-, and system-level safeguards to prevent the misuse of OA mechanisms while preserving their emancipatory intent.

Keywords

Open Access; Authorship ethics; Research integrity; Evaluation metrics; Open Access agreements

Open Access (OA) publishing has become a central pillar of contemporary science policy. Through agreements (sometimes referred to as 'Transformative Open Access agreements') between publishers and research institutions, Article Processing Charges (APCs) are increasingly covered at the institutional level, enabling researchers to publish openly without direct financial burden. These agreements are widely framed as instruments of fairness, accessibility, and global equity (Borrego et al. 2021). Following the emergence of APC-based Open Access models, APCs used to be a direct cost borne by authors or their funders. This created obvious inequities, but it also made financial responsibility transparent and more clearly separable from authorship decisions (Laakso et al. 2011). Agreements between publishers and universities have altered this landscape by converting APC coverage into an institutional asset, often managed centrally and invisibly to individual authors. As a result, access to OA publishing has increasingly become contingent on institutional affiliation rather than contribution. Researchers at well-resourced institutions may enjoy near-frictionless OA publication across major publishers, while others, particularly those at smaller universities or in the Global South (Kwon 2022), remain constrained.

As with many infrastructural reforms, the ethical risks lie not only in implementation failures but in unintended incentive structures. As OA agreements have matured, access to APC funding has increasingly functioned as a form of academic capital; one unevenly distributed across institutions, countries, and career stages. Here we contend that OA coverage can be used as bargaining power to justify authorship or corresponding authorship, decoupled from substantive intellectual contribution. While concerns have been raised about authorship abuse (Khan and Tozal 2025), APC inequities (Khoo 2019), and metric-driven evaluation (Hicks et al. 2015) independently, the specific role of OA agreements as a source of leverage in authorship negotiations – what we refer here to as 'value extraction in OA' – emerges as a new phenomenon. We argue that value extraction represents a distinct integrity risk that is insufficiently addressed by existing authorship and publication ethics frameworks. The issue is not OA itself, but the way in which its institutionalization can be exploited under current academic incentive systems, such as fragmented governance structures embedded within publishing infrastructures, authorship norms, and evaluation metrics that are governed separately and rarely examined in concert.

Value Extraction Enabled by OA Agreements

Concerns about authorship abuse are not new. Practices such as gift authorship, honorary authorship, and coercive authorship are well documented (Strange 2008; Khezr and Mohan 2022; Khan and Tozal 2025). What distinguishes OA-enabled value extraction is its structural character. In these cases, authorship is not primarily exchanged for prestige, hierarchy, or supervision, but for administrative capacity: the ability to cover publication costs through institutional agreements (see e.g. Figure 1).

[Figure 1]

The logic is transactional; access to OA funding is presented as a sufficient contribution to justify authorship or control over the publication process. Corresponding authorship is particularly susceptible. As the locus of interaction with publishers, editors, and APC workflows, corresponding authorship increasingly confers not only administrative responsibility but symbolic ownership of the work. When corresponding authorship is justified primarily by access to OA agreements, there is a blurred boundary between

logistical facilitation and intellectual leadership (ICMJE 2025). We argue that this phenomenon is better understood as 'value extraction': the appropriation of academic credit through control over infrastructural resources rather than through knowledge production. We contend that value extraction in Open Access constitutes a new form of academic misconduct.

Distributional Risks and Power Asymmetries for 'Value Extraction' in Open Access

Distributional Implications

Current authorship guidelines such as those of ICMJE and COPE restrict authorship to intellectual contributions and explicitly exclude financial ones, reflecting assumptions that treat funding as external to authorship negotiations (ICMJE 2025; COPE 2025). As a result, they fail to address contexts in which infrastructural access and APC-based OA agreements function as sources of power capable of systematically shaping authorship practices – an issue that remains largely absent from research integrity debates. The ethical concerns posed by value extraction in OA are magnified by the distributional effects of this practice. These effects operate across multiple, intersecting levels, including global disparities, disciplinary funding differences, institutional resource gaps, intra-institutional inequalities, and individual career stages. Those most vulnerable to OA-enabled value extraction are likely to include early-career researchers, for whom publication pressure is acute and negotiating power is limited; researchers at less-resourced institutions, lacking comprehensive OA agreements; and scholars in the Global South, where APC coverage remains uneven despite the rhetoric of global inclusivity (Borrego 2023; Kwon 2022). In these contexts, offers framed as "support" or "collaboration" may function as de facto coercive choices: accept asymmetrical authorship arrangements or face reduced publication prospects. This risks reproducing dynamics often described as academic colonialism (Sengupta 2021), in which intellectual labor flows from the periphery while credit accrues to those controlling institutional infrastructure.

Structural Drivers of Value Extraction in OA

It would be a mistake to frame value extraction in OA as a matter of a few individual actors. The dynamics described here are incentivized by broader academic structures that shape behavior across roles and career stages: publish-or-perish cultures reward output volume and journal prestige; OA agreements centralize publishing power at the institutional level; and corresponding authorship carries disproportionate symbolic and career value (Hicks et al. 2015). When these elements converge, exploitative dynamics can arise. In fact, any account of value extraction in OA would be incomplete without considering the role of traditional academic performance metrics in shaping these behaviors (DORA 2012; COPE 2025; Hicks et al. 2015). Authorship disputes are embedded in evaluation systems that translate publications into career advancement, funding success, and institutional prestige. Metrics such as publication counts, journal impact factors, h-index scores, and corresponding-authorship positions continue to function, in many evaluative contexts, as proxies for scholarly merit, despite longstanding critiques of their limitations. Within such systems, authorship risks becoming a currency that can be accumulated, exchanged, and strategically optimized. Corresponding authorship occupies a privileged place in this economy. It is often interpreted, rightly or wrongly, as signaling leadership, seniority, or

ownership of the research. When combined with access to OA agreements, corresponding authorship can become a focal point for value extraction: those who control publishing infrastructure can position themselves as indispensable intermediaries between intellectual labor and metric recognition. We argue that, in this context, the offer to “handle APCs” on behalf of someone else should not be treated as a neutral administrative gesture, but should instead be regarded as a means of converting infrastructural access into metric advantage. These dynamics are reinforced by institutional evaluation practices that rarely scrutinize how authorship positions are obtained. Performance assessments typically reward outcomes (publications, citations, journal prestige) while remaining agnostic about the processes that produced them (Moher et al. 2018). This asymmetry creates an ethical blind spot in which behaviors that technically comply with authorship guidelines may nonetheless exploit systemic incentives in ways that undermine fairness and trust.

The interaction between OA agreements and performance metrics thus creates a feedback loop within which value extraction can operate. Metrics incentivize strategic authorship accumulation, including through the phenomenon of value extraction; OA agreements provide the tools to enable it; and the absence of procedural oversight allows these practices to persist. We argue that addressing value extraction in OA requires a critical reassessment of how academic performance is measured and rewarded.

Policy Options and Safeguards for ‘Value Extraction’ in OA

We contend that addressing value extraction in OA does not require abandoning OA agreements or retreating from Open Access. Rather, it requires recognizing that OA agreements introduce new forms of infrastructural power that require explicit governance (Edwards et al. 2013). Safeguards are therefore needed at multiple levels of the research ecosystem.

Institutional Level

At the institutional level, mitigating value extraction in OA requires attention both to publishing procedures and to the evaluative environments in which those procedures acquire meaning. Universities and research organizations should explicitly clarify that access to OA agreements, APC funding, or administrative publishing support cannot, on their own, justify authorship or corresponding authorship without substantial intellectual contribution. While most institutions formally endorse standard authorship criteria, these principles are often articulated independently of the performance metrics through which academic credit is assessed. As a result, institutional signals about what “counts” in evaluation may tacitly undermine commitments to authorship integrity. This tension is particularly salient where corresponding authorship and publication venue are treated as proxies for leadership, productivity, or excellence in hiring, promotion, and funding decisions. Without explicit institutional guidance, some researchers may come to view control over APC logistics as a legitimate pathway to academic recognition, even when intellectual contributions are absent or limited. Institutions may therefore wish to strengthen the role of authorship contribution statements by ensuring that they are reviewed independently of APC approval processes and insulated from evaluative considerations tied to publication metrics. Introducing a procedural firewall where authorship decisions are documented before any discussion of OA coverage could help reduce the risk that

infrastructural access shapes authorship outcomes, whether deliberately or through subtle incentive effects. We also contend that guidance on the ethical use of OA agreements should be explicitly linked to institutional academic evaluation practices.

Publisher Level

Publishers can also play a meaningful role in mitigating value extraction in OA. Given their visibility into authorship patterns across journals and institutions, publishers are well positioned to identify systematic anomalies that may escape institutional oversight. Monitoring patterns of authorship linked to specific OA agreements and “sparse” collaborations could help identify practices that warrant closer scrutiny. In addition, publishers could introduce explicit declarations stating that APC coverage or access to OA agreements played no role in authorship or corresponding authorship decisions. While such declarations would not eliminate misconduct, they could raise awareness of the issue and establish a normative expectation that authorship decisions remain insulated from financial and administrative considerations.

Systemic Level

At the systemic level, addressing value extraction in OA requires expanding research integrity frameworks beyond individual misconduct to include infrastructural power and metric-driven incentives. Traditional integrity models tend to focus on aspects such as conflicts of interest or data manipulation, or ‘honorary’ authorship, while treating publishing infrastructures and evaluation metrics in academia as ethically neutral background conditions. We argue that this assumption is increasingly difficult to sustain. Authorship operates within a performance economy structured by quantitative indicators such as publication counts, journal impact factors, h-indexes, and the symbolic weight of corresponding authorship. These metrics continue, in many academic systems, to function as proxies for scholarly merit in hiring, promotion, and funding decisions, despite widespread recognition of their limitations. In such an environment, authorship becomes a strategic asset, not just a record of contribution. OA agreements interact with these metrics in ethically significant ways. By concentrating publishing access within certain institutions, they enable those who control infrastructural resources to convert administrative capacity into metric advantage. Corresponding authorship, in particular, becomes a critical control point: it signals leadership, confers visibility, and is often privileged in evaluative contexts. When access to OA agreements is used to secure or justify such positions, infrastructural power can be translated into academic credit. Existing evaluation systems rarely interrogate how authorship positions are obtained. Performance assessments reward outputs while remaining largely indifferent to the processes that produced them. This creates a structural blind spot in which practices may formally comply with authorship guidelines yet still exploit systemic asymmetries.

The phenomenon of value extraction in OA thrives precisely in this gap between formal compliance and substantive fairness. Recognizing this dynamic has important implications for research governance. Arguably integrity frameworks should explicitly acknowledge the ethical issues posed by existing publishing infrastructures and the metrics that give them value. Further, initiatives aimed at reforming research assessment, such as DORA or related movements toward narrative evaluation, should incorporate safeguards that decouple infrastructural access to OA publishing from academic credit. Under this lens, the phenomenon of value extraction in OA is a largely predictable outcome of misaligned incentives due to the pitfalls of academic publishing and evaluation metrics in academia.

Conclusion

Open Access agreements were introduced and widely framed as mechanisms to expand access to scientific knowledge and to manage the transition away from subscription-based publishing. This framing, however, has been contested, as OA agreements also serve to stabilize publisher revenue streams and consolidate market structures during the transition to Open Access (Khoo 2019; Borrego et al. 2021; Borrego 2023). Here we presented a new problem posed by Open Access agreements: the phenomenon of value extraction, whereby institutional APC coverage for publication in major journals is leveraged to secure authorship in the absence of substantive intellectual contribution, turning affiliation under such agreements into a form of transactional value. We discussed how this phenomenon undermines authorship integrity and exacerbates existing inequalities. We contend that what may appear as a matter of individual opportunism could be better understood as a largely predictable outcome of misaligned infrastructures, incentives, and evaluation practices in academic publishing and academic evaluation systems based on traditional publication metrics. Open Access implemented within metric-driven systems, and without attention to infrastructural power, may inadvertently reinforce the very hierarchies it aims to dismantle, promoting misconduct including through the newly described phenomenon of value extraction. We believe that recognizing value extraction in Open Access as a new systemic issue is a necessary first step. Arguably, Open Access can fulfill its emancipatory promise only if the conditions under which academic credit is assigned are made transparent, accountable, and aligned with the values it seeks to promote.

Figures

Figure 1. Real example of a co-authorship request in which access to APC funding is presented as a basis for corresponding authorship and collaboration, highlighting how publishing infrastructure can be mobilized as leverage in authorship negotiations – what we refer to as ‘value extraction in Open Access’.

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Declarations of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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